

Exploring Feasibility of Natural Polysaccharides as a Carrier for Solubility and Bioavailability Enhancement of Rosuvastatin Calcium: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

The preferred route for drug delivery is oral administration owing to its convenience, patient compliance, and cost-effectiveness but the researchers are in trouble in the bioavailability. This study was in the aspect of improving the solubility and dissolution rate of Rosuvastatin calcium using the solid dispersion technique with various natural polysaccharides. Both the kneading and solvent evaporation methods were employed to create Solid dispersion formulations with neem gum and tamarind seed powder as natural polysaccharide carriers. The prepared Solid dispersion formulations underwent thorough evaluation, and the most optimized formulation underwent tablet formulation via the direct compression method, followed by quality control testing. Among the various natural polymers screened, Solid dispersion formulations utilizing neem gum demonstrated a significant enhancement in solubility and dissolution. Of the investigated ratios (1:0.5, 1:1, and 1:2), the Solid dispersion formulation with a 1:1 ratio showed the highest solubility enhancement and maximum drug release, alongside favorable surface characteristics as confirmed by Scanning Electronic Microscopic analysis. Subsequently, the prepared core tablet exhibited improved dissolution efficiency, with a 92.34% drug release observed at 60 minutes, outperforming comparative formulations including Physical Mixture-1 (69.5%), Physical Mixture-2 (79.5%), Core Tablet-1 (89.99%), and, Core Tablet-2 (92.34%) the Marketed tablet (88.44%). These results highlight the effectiveness of the optimized Solid dispersion formulation employing natural polysaccharides in significantly improving solubility and dissolution rates, potentially enhancing the solubility and bioavailability of Rosuvastatin calcium. This study contributes to the advancement of pharmaceutical research aimed at enhancing the efficacy and therapeutic outcomes of poorly soluble drugs through innovative formulation strategies.

Keywords: Solid Dispersion, Dissolution Enhancement, Rosuvastatin Calcium, Natural Polysaccharides, Solubility, and Bioavailability.

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Introduction

Rosuvastatin Calcium (RSC), a statin derivative, exerts its cholesterol-lowering effects by inhibiting the enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methyl glutaryl CoA reductase (HMG-CoA reductase), the pivotal enzyme responsible for catalyzing the conversion of mevalonate to cholesterol, thus representing the initial and crucial step in cholesterol biosynthesis. This mechanism underscores its efficacy as a potent lipid-lowering agent, widely prescribed for the management of hyperlipidemia[1-3]. Additionally, RSC finds utility in diverse medical conditions including Alzheimer's disease, benign prostate hyperplasia, and osteoporosis. Despite being classified as a BCS class II medication, RSC

exhibits limited bioavailability (approximately 20%) and poor water solubility (0.33 mg/ml), primarily attributed to its crystalline nature[3]. The crystallinity of RSC impedes its dissolution and subsequent absorption, thereby hindering its therapeutic efficacy. To address these challenges, innovative pharmaceutical strategies have been pursued, aiming to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of RSC for improved clinical outcomes. Recent advancements in drug delivery systems have focused on developing formulations to overcome the inherent limitations of RSC. Solid dispersion techniques utilizing various carriers have garnered significant attention. These formulations

aim to disperse the drug within a solid matrix, thereby enhancing its solubility and dissolution rate, ultimately facilitating improved bioavailability. Through meticulous formulation development and optimization, novel solid dispersion formulations of RSC have demonstrated promising results in preclinical and clinical studies[4]. These formulations leverage the synergistic effects of natural polymers, such as neem gum and tamarind seed powder, to enhance drug solubility and dissolution kinetics.

The pursuit of innovative pharmaceutical formulations for RSC underscores the commitment to advancing therapeutic efficacy and patient outcomes in the management of hyperlipidemia and other related disorders. By addressing the challenges associated with its limited solubility and bioavailability, these advancements hold the potential to optimize the therapeutic utility of RSC, thereby enhancing its clinical impact in the treatment of various medical conditions. Neem gum, derived from the bark of *Azadirachta indica*, and tamarind seed powder, sourced from *Tamarindus indica* seeds, exhibit distinctive attributes rendering them optimal candidates as carriers in solid dispersion formulations. These natural polymers proffer advantages such as cost-effectiveness, biodegradability, and non-toxicity, thus presenting appealing options for pharmaceutical applications[5]. By incorporating RSC into solid dispersions with neem gum and tamarind seed powder as carriers, researchers aspire to enhance its solubility, consequently elevating its oral bioavailability. This, in turn, holds promise for yielding superior treatment outcomes for hyperlipidaemic conditions, encompassing cholesterol reduction and mitigating the risk of cardiovascular ailments[2,4-5].

This research work embarks on an exploration of the formulation development of RSC, harnessing neem gum and tamarind seed powder as natural carriers through the SD method. Through a meticulous review of pertinent literature and empirical evidence, the efficacy and viability of this approach in augmenting the therapeutic potential of RSC for hyperlipidemia treatment shall be illuminated. Additionally, elucidation on the mechanism of SD and insights into natural polymers' role in enhancing solubility and bioavailability will be delved into, enriching the scientific discourse surrounding this research.

Materials and Methods

Materials: RSC was received as a gift sample by NTK Pharma Pvt. Ltd. (Maharashtra, India). Following chemicals were purchased: and chemicals are donated as gifts as samples like sodium hydroxide (Nice chemicals), magnesium stearate (Phoenix Biologicals Pvt. Ltd.), microcrystalline

cellulose (Nice chemicals), crospovidone (Phoenix Biologicals Pvt. Ltd.), PVP K30 (Loba Chemie), aerosil (Phoenix Biologicals Pvt. Ltd.), methanol (Changshu Hongsheng Fine Chemical Co., Ltd) and ethanol (Changshu Hongsheng Fine Chemical Co., Ltd). All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

Methodology

Pre-formulation studies: Pre-formulation, a process that emerged in the late 1950s and early 1960s, is a method of developing stable and bioavailable dosage forms for pharmaceutical products. It focuses on the physicochemical properties of a new drug candidate, which can impact its performance and dosage form development [6]. This information can be crucial for formulation design or molecular modification. Each drug has inherent chemical and physical properties that are considered before pharmaceutical formulation development.

The objective of pre-formulation studies is to create an elegant, stable, effective, and safe dosage form by establishing kinetic rate profiles, compatibility with other ingredients, and determining the physicochemical parameters of new drug substances[7]. Key properties include drug solubility, partition coefficient, dissolution rate, polymorphic forms, and stability. Polymorphisms in crystal and amorphous forms can provide different chemical, physical, and therapeutic descriptions of the drug molecule[6,8].

Organoleptic properties: Color, Odor, and Taste of the drug was recorded using descriptive terminology [8].

Melting point: The melting point of RSC is determined by packing the drug powder in a capillary tube (the substance should be standing in the capillary 3-4 mm from the bottom of the packed capillary tube), sealing it, and wetting it with the liquid in a bath. The tube is then placed on a thermometer stand and adjusted to stand opposite the mercury bulb.

The thermometer is then placed in a beaker containing paraffin oil, heated slowly and constantly stirring. When the substance shows signs of liquefaction, the burner is removed and the temperature is recorded [9,10].

$\lambda_{\max}$ Determination:

The standard RSC stock solution is prepared by dissolving 10 mg of the drug in a 100 ml volumetric flask using phosphate buffer at pH 6.8, and the working standard solutions are scanned in the UV range to obtain absorbance [11].

Solubility Study: To figure out the solubility of RSC, it was dissolved in 0.1 N HCL, phosphate

buffer (pH 6.8), distilled water, methanol, ethanol, dimethyl formamide, and dimethyl sulfoxide. In a mechanical shaker, the sample was shaken for 8 hours at 37° C. Using Whatman filter paper, the supernatant was filtered, and the filtrate's UV visible spectrophotometer was used to measure its wavelength of 241 nm [11-13].

Preparation of 0.1 N Hydrochloric Acid: 8.5 ml of HCl was transferred into a 1000 ml volumetric flask and made up the volume with distilled water [11, 14].

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer (pH-6.8): 6.80 g of potassium Dihydrogen orthophosphate and 0.90 g of sodium hydroxide were accurately dissolved in 1000 ml of distilled water [11, 14].

Standard Calibration Curve of Rosuvastatin Calcium in 0.1 N HCL: Precisely measure out 100 mg of RSC and pour it into a 100 ml volumetric flask with 5 ml of methanol. Next, fill the volumetric flask to the meniscus with pH 1.2 acid buffer, bringing the concentration of the primary stock solution to 1000 µg/ml. Now pipette out 10 ml of this main stock solution into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Use an acid buffer pH 1.2 to get the volume up to 100 ml, containing 100 µg of medication per milliliter. Once more, take 10 ml using a pipette and transfer it to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add acid buffer pH 1.2 to get the volume up to 100 ml, which has a medication concentration of 10 µg/ml. Pipette 1 ml, 2 ml, 3 ml, 4 ml, 5 ml, 6 ml, 7 ml, 8 ml, 9 ml, and 10 ml into a 10 ml volumetric flask. After that, adjust the volume to 10 ml using an acid buffer with a pH of 1.2. At 241 nm, the medication concentration's absorbance was found in the UV spectrophotometer.

Plotting the calibration curve involved placing the absorbance on the Y-axis and the concentration on the X-axis [11, 14-15].

Standard Calibration Curve of Rosuvastatin Calcium in Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8: Precisely measure out 100 mg of RSC and pour it into a 100 ml volumetric flask with 5 ml of methanol. Next, fill the volumetric flask to the meniscus with pH 6.8 basic buffer, bringing the concentration of the primary stock solution to 1000 µg/ml. Now pipette out 10 ml of this main stock solution into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Use an acid buffer pH 6.8 to get the volume up to 100 ml, containing 100 µg of medication per milliliter. Once more, take 10 ml using a pipette and concentration of the primary stock solution to 1000 µg/ml. Now pipette out 10 ml of this main stock solution into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Use an acid buffer pH 6.8 to get the volume up to 100 ml, containing 100 µg of medication per

milliliter. Once more, take 10 ml using a pipette and transfer it to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add acid buffer pH 6.8 to get the volume up to 100 ml, which has a medication concentration of 10 µg/ml. Pipette 1 ml, 2 ml, 3 ml, 4 ml, 5 ml, 6 ml, 7 ml, 8 ml, 9 ml, and 10 ml into a 10 ml volumetric flask. After that, adjust the volume to 10 ml using an acid buffer with a pH of 6.8. At 241 nm, the medication concentration's absorbance was found in the UV spectrophotometer. Plotting the calibration curve involved placing the absorbance on the Y-axis and the concentration on the X-axis [11, 14-15].

Phase Solubility Study of Drugs with Different Percentages of Carriers: An excess amount of RSC was added to a volumetric flask containing 10 ml of aqueous carrier (pH 1.2 and 6.8 buffers) of tamarind seed powder, neem gum at 1% w/v, 2% w/v, 4% w/v, and 8% w/v concentrations and placed in a Mechanical shaker and agitated at room temperature for 8 hours. The solutions were filtered and analyzed at 241 nm by using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The study was performed in triplicates [16].

Preparation of Physical Mixture: A physical mixture of RSC with carriers like Tamarind seed powder and Neem gum at a different drug:carrier ratio (1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, and 1:8) was prepared by mixing the accurately weighed quantity of drug and polymer in a glass mortar with the help of pestle. This mixture was then subsequently passed through sieve number 60 and stored in a desiccator for 24 h [11, 16].

Preparation of Solid Dispersion by Kneading Method: A weighed quantity of a mixture of RSC and tamarind seed powder (Figure 1) (composition described in Table 1) was placed in a mortar, and the mixture was kneaded thoroughly for 20 min with ethanol (1.5 times the amount of mixture). The kneaded mixture was dried in an oven at 60°C until it reached a constant weight, pulverized, and screened using sieve no. 80 [11, 17-23].

Preparation of Solid Dispersion Using Solvent Evaporation Method: In this method, RSC was dissolved in organic solvent and the Neem gum (Figure 1) (composition described in Table 1) was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water, then the drug and carrier were mixed and try to get a clear solution.

After the entire dissolution, the solvent was evaporated.

The solid mass was ground, dried at 60° C, pulverized, and screened using sieve no. 80 [11,17-18].

Preparation of Solid Dispersion

Figure 1: Formulation of Solid dispersion and Core Tablet Formulation

Formulation Chart of Solid Dispersion

Table 1: Formulation chart of Solid Dispersion

S. No	Formulation	Solid dispersion method	Composition (Drug: Carrier)	Ratio (Drug: Carrier)
1	SD1	Kneading Method	RSC+ Tamarind Seed Powder	100:50
2	SD2		RSC+ Tamarind Seed Powder	100:100
3	SD3		RSC+ Tamarind Seed Powder	100:200
4	SD4	Solvent Evaporation Method	RSC+ Neem Gum	100:50
5	SD5		RSC+ Neem Gum	100:100
6	SD6		RSC+ Neem Gum	100:200

* All weights are expressed in milligrams

Evaluation of Solid Dispersion

Drug Content: Solid Dispersion containing 50 mg was weighed accurately and dissolved in 50 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The solution was filtered and RSC content was analyzed by observing absorbance in a UV-spectrometer at 241nm [19-23].

Saturation Solubility: Pure drugs and SDs in excess quantity were placed in volumetric flasks containing 10 ml of pH 6.8 buffer. The samples were placed in a mechanical shaker at 37°C and 50 rpm for 8 hr.

The solutions were analyzed by UV-spectrophotometer [19-23].

FTIR Spectroscopy: FTIR spectra of the drug and their formulations were carried out by using FT-IR Spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU, Japan).

Each formula (5 mg) was mixed with about 100 mg Potassium bromide was compressed into discs under pressure of 10,000 to 15,000 pounds per square inch.

The IR spectra were recorded using an infrared spectrophotometer [11].

Pre-Compression Parameters: In pharmaceutical tablet formulation, assessing pre-compression parameters is crucial to ensure the quality and efficacy of the final product.

The pre-compression parameters, including tapped density, bulk density, compressibility index, Hausner ratio, and angle of repose, were evaluated for the prepared batches intended for tablet compression, following the Indian Pharmacopeia Standards [11, 20-23].

Formulation Chart of Core Tablet: The composition of RSC core tablets is depicted in Table 2. All of the powders used are passed through Sieve No. 45 separately.

Rosuvastatin calcium, PVP K30, crospovidone, and microcrystalline cellulose are mixed by the geometric addition technique. Aerosil and magnesium stearate are then added to the mixed powders.

Finally, the direct compression of 300 mg of the blend was weighed and compressed by a tablet

punching machine equipped with 10 mm flat-faced punches[11].

Table 2: Formulation chart of Core tablet

Ingredients	CT1	C T2
RSC & Tamarind Seed Powder	20	20
PVP K30	10	10
Crospovidone	15	15
Microcrystalline cellulose	251	251
Aerosil	2	2
Magnesium stearate	2	2
Total weight	300	300

* All weights are expressed in milligrams
 CT 1 (Pure drug+ Excipients); CT 2 (SD5 + Excipients)

Post-Compression Parameter: The physical parameters, including uniformity of weight, hardness, friability, disintegration time, and drug content, were evaluated for the prepared batches as per Indian Pharmacopeia Standards [11].

Statistical Analysis: Selected studies were performed in triplicate and the values were expressed as mean ± S.D. The data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA test.

Scanning Electron Microscopy: Comparisons were undertaken using a scanning electron microscope after morphological analysis of the manufactured formulation and coarse medication was completed. We used carbon double-sided tape to test each sample on a brass stub. A sputter coater operating at 2.0 kV at 25 mA for ten minutes coated the samples in gold (thickness = 15–20 nm). The investigations employed an excitation voltage of 20 kV [11, 16].

In-vitro Drug Release Studies: A study on the *in-vitro* dissolving of pure drugs, physical mixture-1, physical mixture-2, formulation of SDs, and marketed tablets was conducted using the USP type 2 (paddle) dissolution apparatus method in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. 900 ml of pH 6.8 buffer were stirred at a speed of 75 revolutions per minute for 120 minutes, while the temperature was kept at

37±0.5°C. At sampling intervals, 5 ml dissolution samples were taken out, and each time, 5 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added back into the dissolution medium.

After passing the solution through the Whatman filter paper, the absorbance at 241nm was measured using a UV Spectrophotometer to quantify the drug concentration in the aliquots that were removed.

After calculating the concentration using the conventional plot, the results were plotted as the cumulative percentage of drug release over time [11,16,20].

Result

Pre-Formulation Studies of the Drug

Organoleptic Properties: Physical observation of the drug revealed that RSC is a white solid powder.

Melting Point: The melting point of RSC was found to be in the range of 121°C-124°Cthe reported melting point of the drug was found at 122°C, hence experimental values were in good agreement with official values.

λmax Determination: The maximum absorption of RSC was found to be 241 nm represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Absorption Maxima of RSC

Solubility study: Solubility of RSC in different solvents (Table 3), RSC shows significant solubility in the biological solvent at pH 6.8, additionally, the calibration curve results to support the solubility profile.

Table 3: Solubility data of RSC in different solvents

Physiological solvent	Solubility
pH 1.2 buffer	255.0±0.018 mg/ml
pH 6.8 buffer	700.0±0.05 mg/ml
Distilled water	369.3±0.028 mg/ml
Ethanol	0.86±0.0072mg/1000ml
Methanol	0.95±0.0089 mg/ml
DMSO	14 ±0.01mg/ml
Dimethyl formamide	11.22±0.109 mg/ml

*Solubility at 37±0.5°C(n=3)

Determination of Standard Calibration Curve

Standard Curve in 0.1N HCl: A graph of absorbances versus concentration was plotted, which was found to be linear over the range of mcg/ml indicating its compliance with Beer’s law. Results as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Calibration curve of RSC in pH 1.2 phosphate buffer solution

Standard Curve in Phosphate Buffer: A graph of absorbances versus concentration was plotted, which was found to be linear over the range of mcg/ml indicating its compliance with Beer’s law. Results as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Standard calibration curve of RSC in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Assay: The percentage purity of the drug was calculated by using the calibration curve method.

The percentage purity of RSC was found to be 98.99% w/v.

RSC Pure Drug

Inferences: The IR spectrum was measured in the solid state as KBr dispersion. The IR spectrum of RSC is similar to the reported peaks of RSC.

Drug-Carriers Interaction Study

Inferences: The major peaks were obtained in the pure drug in the same characteristic bands without any significant spectral changes.

The FT-IR peak of spectra for Tamarind seed powder and Neem gum containing solid dispersion showed No shift and No Disappearance of the characteristic peaks suggesting that there is No Interaction between the drugs and indicating that they were chemically compatible.

Phase Solubility Study: The phase solubility result of RSC with different carriers was found in the below table 4.

Table 4: Phase Solubility Data of Various Carriers in Physiological Solution

% Carriers	pH 6.8 buffer	pH 1.2 buffer
	% Solubility	% Solubility
Tamarind Seed Powder 3%	24.96	0.256
Tamarind Seed Powder 6%	55.89	0.7668
Neem Gum 3%	49.93	2.676
Neem Gum 6%	74.89	6.558

Drug Content: The drug content of the solid dispersions SD 2, and SD 5 was found to be 96.1% and 97.96 %. The carrier concentration increased the drug dispersed to the carriers decreased shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Drug content in the solid dispersions

Saturation Solubility: The saturation solubility increased with an increased with an increase in carrier concentration. This might be due to better wetting ability associated with the carrier. Formulation SD 5 shows more concentration of drug solubility. The saturation solubility of prepared solid dispersion is represented in Table 5.

Table 5: Saturation solubility

Formulation	Ratio	% Solubility
Pure Drug	----	0.28
SD 1	1:0.5	21.33
SD 2	1:1	37.47
SD 3	1:2	30.43
SD 4	1:0.5	25.48
SD 5	1:1	64.54
SD 6	1:2	44.12

Scanning electron microscopy: Scanning electron microscopy was carried out to study the surface morphology of particles. It was found that the SD 5 of RSC revealed a smooth texture as shown in Fig.6. The SEM picture of pure drug particles was found abundantly with larger particle sizes when compared to the SD formulation. Thus, the optimized

formulation of RSC- produced better surface characteristics.

The surface structure of optimized SD in the SEM appeared good in shape. This micrograph agreed with those measured by particle size distribution.

Figure 6: (A): SEM of RSC, (B) SEM of optimized formulation SD

Evaluations for Core Tablet Preparation

Pre-formulation studies of Drug, Polymer & Excipients: Physical characteristics, such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, and Hausner's ratio, were used to characterize the drugs, polymers, and excipients. The physical properties of all materials were within the acceptable range, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Pre-compression parameters of Drug, Polymers & Excipients

Ingredients	Angle of repose(Θ)	Bulk density (g/cc)	Tapped density (g/cc)	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
RSC	25°87	0.5476±0.004	0.611±0.005	10.88	1.124
PVP K 30	22°57	0.710±00.006	0.723±0.015	14.129	1.188
Crospovidone	24 °56	0.470±0.002	0.615±0.005	13.100	1.140
MCC	30 °51	0.4572±0.004	0.326±0.002	9.771	1.19
Aerosil	28°13	0.843±0.006	0.842±0.007	11.924	1.12
Mag. Stearate	33 °43	0.242±0.001	0.310±0.003	10.39	1.107

Mean ±SD (n=3)

Pre-Compression Parameters of Core Tablet Granules

Angle of Repose: The prepared powder blends are evaluated for their flow properties (table 7). The resistance offered to the movement of particles can be judged by the angle of repose. It provides a qualitative and quantitative assessment of internal cohesive and frictional forces under a low level of external load applied during mixing and tableting. The angles of repose of all three samples were within the range of 19–21°. These values indicate that the powder blend had good flow properties.

Bulk Density & Tapped Density: The powdered blends are evaluated for bulk density and tapped density by using bulk density apparatus, and the

results are shown in Table 7. The bulk density was found in the range of 0.459±0.33 to 0.414±0.39 gm/cc. The tapped density ranged between 0.563±0.39 to 0.672±0.34 gm/cc. Which indicates that powder is loosely packed. These values were then used to calculate Carr's index and Hausner's ratio to check the flow ability of powder.

Carr's Index & Hausner's ratio: The Compressibility index exists in the range between 12.39±0.27 & 13.54±0.29. The Hausner's ratio of all samples between 1.106±0.25 & 1.074±0.16 is shown the Table 6. These values indicate that the prepared blends possessed minimum interparticulate interactions and good flow properties which is a preliminary requirement for formulating the tablets.

Table 7: Pre-compression parameters of Core granules

Sample	Angle of repose(Θ)	Bulk density (g/cc)	Tapped density (g/cc)	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
CT 1	21° 80	0.414±0.29	0.672±0.34	12.39±0.27	1.106±0.25
CT 2	19° 61	0.459±0.31	0.563±0.39	13.54±0.29	1.074±0.16

Mean ±SD (n=6)

Post-Compression Parameters of Core Tablets:

The tablets were light brown in color, flat in shape, and had a fine surface. The hardness of all sample tablets was adjusted to 3 kg/cm². The friability of all three samples of tablets was within 1%, which was an indication of the good mechanical resistance of the tablet.

The drug content of the formulations C T1 and C T2 is 97.23 to 97.75%. The thickness is measured for all tablets and found to be within the acceptable range.

The weight of the tablet varied between 295.1±0.52 to 312.2±0.91 mg, as represented in Table 8.

The variation in weight was within the range of ± 5% complying with pharmaceutical specifications. Disintegration time is essential for drug delivery from tablets, which are designed for the rapid bursting of granules.

The *in-vitro* disintegration times of prepared tablets range between 24 and 26 sec. This is due to the preparation of the tablets using Croscopovidone showed rapid disintegration in 26 sec.

Table 8: Post-Compression Parameters of Core Tablets

Sample	**Average weight	*Hardness	*Thickness	**Friability	DT (seconds)	Drug content
CT 1	295.1±0.52	3.2±0.24	4.9±0.39	0.603±0.05	24	97.23
CT 2	312.2±0.91	2.9±0.19	3.9±0.245	0.398±0.01	26	98.01

Mean SD*(n=6), Mean SD**(n=20)

In-vitro Release Studies: The release profile of the formulations was determined by using USP dissolution apparatus type 2. The formulation product was placed in the dissolution flask containing a pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solution. Then the paddle was rotated at 75 rpm, and immediately a liquid of 5 ml sample was withdrawn at every interval up to 120 min. The drug content was determined at 241nm by using a UV spectrophotometer. The *In-vitro* drug release studies were performed to evaluate the release of the evaluated formulation. The cumulative percentage

release in pH 6.8 buffer for Pure drug, PM-1, PM-2, CT 1, CT 2, and marketed drugs were recorded and the SD showed higher drug release, respectively 75.46%, 69.5%, 79.5%, 89.99%, 92.34%, and 88.44% within 120 minutes.

The cumulative amounts of drug released from the Pure drug, PM-1, PM-2, CT 2, CT5, and marketed drug are shown in Figure 7. The formulated Solid dispersion with carrier neem gum showed a greater rate of dissolution.

Figure 7: In-vitro Dissolution Graph Marketed Tablet, Pure Drug, PMs, CT1 and CT2

Discussion

First and earliest step in the manufacture of cholesterol, mevalonate is converted to cholesterol by the enzyme HMG-CoA reductase, which is inhibited by a statin derivative that lowers cholesterol levels. It is a strong lipid-lowering medication used to treat people with high blood cholesterol [1-3]. One of the statin derivatives RSC is a BCS class II drug, its crystalline structure results in low water solubility (0.33 mg/ml) and restricted bioavailability (20%) [3-6,10-11]. This study investigates the use of natural polysaccharides, specifically neem gum and tamarind seed powder, as carriers to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of RSC through solid dispersion (SD) techniques based on the review by Avinash *et al.* 2022 [22].

Both the kneading and solvent evaporation methods were employed to create SD formulations, which is the most preferred method in the formulation and development sector to increase the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs by yielding several key findings. Sibi *et al.* 2024 have performed solubility enhancement of RSC by using the various generations of carriers/polymers and proposed significant results as the Neem gum and Tamarind seed powder significantly improved the solubility and dissolution rate of RSC, with the 1:1 drug-to-carrier-ratio- (SD 2 & SD 5 formulation) demonstrating the highest solubility and drug release profile. As the research was performed, the evaluation parameter suggested that the neem gum shows a significant increase in solubility of RSC and this was achieved by the selection of solvent evaporation method, which ensure uniform molecular-level distribution and smaller particle size, when solvent was evaporated. Often leads to finer particles due to molecular dispersion and subsequent solvent removal, which increase the surface area available for dissolution. The solvent also facilitates better interaction and potential molecular dispersion of the drug within the cellular matrix, promoting a more amorphous, and therefore more soluble. SEM analysis revealed favorable surface characteristics for the SD formulations which are much more significant than previously reported. Drug content analysis confirmed high drug loading efficiency in the optimized SD formulations with a ratio of 1:1 in both carriers. Among the core tablet formulations, CT 2 showed the highest drug release (92.34% at 60 minutes), surpassing other formulations and the marketed tablet. Pre-compression studies indicated excellent flow properties of the powder blends, suggesting ease of handling and processing. Post-compression parameters, including uniformity of weight, hardness, friability, and disintegration time, were within pharmacopeial limits, ensuring the quality and reliability of the tablets. Tamarind seed powder is a polysaccharide that can also effectively increase

the solubility of statin derivatives, but typically to a lesser extent when compared to solvent evaporation method because of homogeneity of mixing (mechanical mixing may not achieve the same level so, less drug and carrier interaction), particle size reduction (produce coarse mixture, as it relies on physical blending and limited liquid addition, leading to large particle size and reduced dissolution rate), and wettability and surface area were not achieved, as the drug may not be finely dispersed within the carrier matrix. As a result, the solid depression made by the method of solid dispersion method using neem gum as a carrier has appreciated better homogeneity of mixing, particle size reduction, drug carrier interaction, wettability, and surface area for better dissolution aspects.

Conclusion

Natural polysaccharides like neem gum and tamarind seed powder are promising carriers for enhancing the solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs like RSC. The study concludes that natural polysaccharides such as neem gum and tamarind seed powder are effective carriers in SD formulations to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs like RSC. This approach could significantly improve therapeutic efficacy and patient outcomes for medications with limited solubility and bioavailability to appreciate better therapeutic action in the treatment of hyperlipidemia. Further research and clinical studies are recommended to validate these findings and explore their broader applications in pharmaceutical formulations. AI can be used in pharmaceutical development to optimize drug formulations by predicting the best combinations of carriers and methods for solubility enhancement. Machine learning algorithms can analyze vast datasets to identify patterns and predict effective formulations. AI-driven molecular modeling can simulate interactions between RSC and carriers, helping in selecting promising carriers and methods for solid dispersion. AI can automate kneading and solvent evaporation processes, ensuring consistency and precision in SD formulation production. It can predict pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles, providing insights into clinical efficacy and safety. This can accelerate drug development, reduce time and costs, and bring effective treatments to market faster.

References

1. Samizo S, Kaneko H. Predictive Modeling of HMG-CoA Reductase Inhibitory Activity and Design of New HMG-CoA Reductase Inhibitors. *ACS omega*. 2023 Jul 18;8(30):27247-55.
2. Holdgate GA, Ward WH, McTaggart F. Molecular mechanism for inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl CoA (HMG-CoA)

- reductase by rosuvastatin. *Biochemical Society Transactions*. 2003 Jun 1;31(3):528-31.
3. Kaur, L., T. Kaur, A. P. Singh, And A. P. Singh. Formulation Development and Solubility Enhancement of Rosuvastatin Calcium by Using Hydrophilic Polymers and Solid Dispersion Method. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 13, 2021.
 4. Lovepreet Kaur, Taranjit Kaur, Amar Pal Singh, Ajeet Pal Sing, formulation development and solubility enhancement of rosuvastatin calcium by using hydrophilic polymers and solid dispersion method, *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*, 2021;13(6):50-55.
 5. Tekade AR, Yadav JN. A review on solid dispersion and carriers used therein for solubility enhancement of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Advanced pharmaceutical bulletin*. 2020 Jul;10(3):359.
 6. Dosage Forms, Formulation Developments and Regulations by Amit Nayak and Kalyan Kumar Sen (2023).
 7. Lachmann L, Liebermann HA, Kiang JL. The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy. 3rd ed. Bombay: Varghese Publishing House (1998): p.430-40.
 8. Lieberman HA, Lachman L, Schwartz JB. *Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms: tablets*. 2 nd ed: New York: Marcel Dekker, Inc.; 2005 (3) 77-160.
 9. *Advanced practical organic chemistry*- N.K. Vishnoi, 21-22, Vikas Publishing and distributor.
 10. Abdullah Ali H, Kamal Omer H. Solubility Enhancement of a Poorly Water-Soluble Drug Using Hydrotrophy and Mixed Hydrotrophy-Based Solid Dispersion Techniques. *Advances in Pharmacological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022 Nov 28;2022.
 11. Sibi K, Mohanraj KP, Kumar SS, Gowrishankar C, and Karthick P: Dissolution enhancement of rosuvastatin calcium by using various generations of hydrophilic polymers; a comparative study. *Int J pharma sci & Res* 2024;15(2):1000-11.
 12. Indian Pharmacopeia Commission. *Indian Pharmacopeia 2022*. Ghaziabad: Indian Pharmacopeia Commission; 2022.
 13. Kumar, A. P., & Kumar, D. (2021). Determination of Pharmaceuticals by UV-Visible Spectrophotometry. *Current Pharmaceutical Analysis*, 17(9), 1156-1170.
 14. Leuner C and Dressman J (2000). Improving drug solubility for oral delivery using solid dispersions. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 50: 47-60.
 15. Mandale DA, Nauman MM, Janvi M, Isha M, Nandini M, Hasan M, Chauhan NN. Solubility Enhancement of Rosuvastatin Calcium Using Solvent Evaporation Technique., *JETIR.*, May 2023; 10(5): 229-257.
 16. Mohanraj Palanisamy and Jasmina Khanam, solid state characterization and improvement of dissolution profile Solid dispersion of prednisolone. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*, 2011, 37(4): 373–386 © 2011.
 17. Rodde MS, Divase GT, Devkar TB, Tekade AR. Solubility and bioavailability enhancement of poorly aqueous soluble atorvastatin: in vitro, ex vivo, and in vivo studies. *BioMed Research International*. 2014;2014(1):463895.
 18. Cid AG, Simonazzi A, Palma SD, Bermúdez JM. Solid dispersion technology as a strategy to improve the bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. *Therapeutic delivery*. 2019 May 16;10(6):363-82.
 19. Abdullah Ali H, Kamal Omer H. Solubility Enhancement of a Poorly Water-Soluble Drug Using Hydrotrophy and Mixed Hydrotrophy-Based Solid Dispersion Techniques. *Advances in Pharmacological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022;2022(1):7161660.
 20. Panda TK, Das D, Panigrahi L. Formulation development of solid dispersions of bosentan using Gelucire 50/13 and Poloxamer 188. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. 2016 Sep 26;6(9):027-33.
 21. Inam S, Irfan M, Lali NU, Khalid Syed H, Asghar S, Khan IU, Khan SU, Iqbal MS, Zaheer I, Khames A, Abou-Taleb HA. Development and characterization of eudragit® EPO-based solid dispersion of rosuvastatin calcium to foresee the impact on solubility, dissolution, and antihyperlipidemic activity. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2022 Apr 18;15(4):492.
 22. Anitha B, Praveen Kumar CH, Susmitha J, Krishna PR. Formulation and Evaluation of Prolonged-Release Tablets Containing Solid Dispersions of Rosuvastatin Calcium. *Future Journal of Pharmaceuticals and Health Sciences*. 2021;1(4):180-5.
 23. Eisa AM, El-Megrab NA, El-Nahas HM. Formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving tablets of haloperidol solid dispersion. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2022 Nov 1; 30(11): 1589-602.